

ШЕОРОН ВИНІТ

студент, підготовительне відділення, НАУ «ХАІ».

*Научный руководитель – Шленёва М.Г., к.ф.н., доц., каф. 801,
ф-т міжнародних комунікацій і підготовки іноземних громадян,
НАУ «ХАІ».*

RESEARCH OF PHYTOCOMPONENTS FOR TREATMENT OF MALARIA AND COVID 19

The development of science in the world is very fruitful. Scientists around the world have made particular progress in the field of medicine. Professors from the University of Buea made amazing discoveries in the usefulness of phytochemicals for the treatment of malaria and other virus diseases in Africa. Malaria remains one of the leading and dangerous public problems of health care in Africa. Today, antimalarial drugs not only treat this disease but are also used to treat COVID 19.

In recent times, this situation becomes worse with the increasing spread of plasmodium drug-resistant strains. Therefore, new antimalarial drugs are urgently needed to treat the population. Traditional healers have long used plants for the prevention and treatment of infections. Professors of the University of Buea examines the current state of botanical screening in Africa and also conducts experimental studies of anti-malarial plants that have a strong antiviral effect. These experiments indicate that in Africa, were used 217 different species as antiviral drugs in folk medicine. 26 of 217 species gives a hundred phytochemicals, some of them are potential sources of the development of new anti-malaria (antibodies). The study involved three age groups (group 1 — 5 years old, group 2 — 5–15 years old, group 3 — over 15 years old). Mosquitoes captured indoors on human volunteers were identified morphologically. Species of the *Anopheles gambiae* have been identified by polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Mosquito infection was detected by enzyme immunoassay and PCR.

Raw extracts and/or essential oils prepared from 54 other species affected on Plasmodium SPP, as well as on other sources of viral stamps. His study shows that the African flora represents a high potential for new antiviral compounds that together treat malaria and other viral diseases.

For the full use of herbal remedies in world medical practice, further ethnobotanical studies and laboratory studies are necessary.

References:

1. Titanji VP, Zofou D, Ngemenya MN. (2008) The antimalarial potential of medicinal plants used for the treatment of malaria in Cameroonian folk

- medicine. Afr J Tradit Complement Altern Med. Vol. 10;5(3), pp. 302-321.
2. Anna Longdoh Njunda, Charles Njumkeng, Shey Dickson Nsagha, Jules Clement Nguedia Assob, Tebit Emmanuel Kwenti (2016) The prevalence of malaria in people living with HIV in Yaounde, Cameroon, BMC Public Health, Vol. 16: 964. doi: 10.1186/s12889-016-3647-z

ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ФІТОКОМПОНЕНТІВ ДЛЯ ЛІКУВАННЯ МАЛЯРІЇ ТА COVID 19

У статті розглядається досвід вченого співтовариства щодо ефективності африканських рослин при лікуванні малярії та штамів нових вірусних захворювань.

Ключові слова: *фітокомпоненти, протималярійні препарати, штами, Африка*

RESEARCH OF PHYTOCOMPONENTS FOR TREATMENT OF MALARIA AND COVID 19

The article examines the experience of the scientific community on the effectiveness of African plants in the treatment of malaria and strains of new viral diseases.

Key words: *phytocomponents, antimalarial drugs, strains, Africa*